

Technische Universität Dresden
Bereich Mathematik und Naturwissenschaften
Fakultät Physik
Institut für Kern- und Teilchenphysik
Abt. Laser-Teilchenbeschleunigung
Institut für Strahlenphysik
HZDR, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf

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Synthetic characterization of ultrashort electron bunches using transition radiation

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Finn-Ole Carstens
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Erstgutachter: Prof. Dr. Ulrich Schramm
Zweitgutachter: Prof. Dr. Thomas Cowan

Zusammenfassung

Diese Arbeit beschreibt das in-situ *CTR plugin* für den Particle-in-Cell Code *PIConGPU*.

Dieses C++-Plugin berechnet die kohärente Übergangsstrahlung (Coherent Transition Radiation, CTR) von Millionen bis zu Milliarden Makroteilchen in *PIConGPU* Plasma Simulationen. Um sowohl eine immense Datenausgabe von hunderten von GB bis TB auf Festplatten, als auch eine zeitintensive Nachbearbeitung auf wenigen CPUs zu verhindern, wurde das Plugin auf GPUs parallelisiert als in-situ Teil *PIConGPUs* implementiert.

Die Physik des Plugins wurde erfolgreich implementiert und mit einer ursprünglichen python Implementation, welche wiederum mit der analytischen Theorie bestätigt wurde, getestet und mit durchschnittlichen Abweichungen von weniger als 1% verifiziert. Zusätzlich wurden Benchmarks zu dem Plugin erstellt, die zeigen, dass man komplette Übergangsstrahlungsspektren in wenigen Minuten berechnen kann.

Anschließend wurde das *CTR plugin* in LWFA Simulationen mit, von selbst oder durch eine "Downramp" injizierten, Elektronen-Pulsen genutzt. Dabei imitiert das Plugin mehrfache hypothetische Platzierungen von Übergangsstrahlungsfolien über die gesamte LWFA Länge und es wurde beobachtet, wie die Entwicklung des Elektronenpulses zu charakteristischen Merkmalen im Übergangsstrahlungsspektrum führt.

Dieses neue Werkzeug ist eine synthetische Diagnostikmethode, welche es ermöglicht, die Übergangsstrahlungsdaten von Experimenten direkt mit Simulationen zu vergleichen. In zukünftigen Experimenten kann es Einblicke in die longitudinalen Profile von Elektronenpulsen in fs-Länge gewähren, welches für zukünftige, kompakte, durch LWFA angetriebene freie Elektronen Laser benötigt wird.

Abstract

This work describes the in-situ *CTR plugin* for the particle-in-cell code *PICongPU*. The C++ -plugin calculates coherent transition radiation (CTR) from millions to billions of macro-particles in a PICongPU plasma simulation. In order to avoid excessive disk output of many GB to TB of data, as well as and extensive post-processing runtimes on only few CPUs, the plugin was parallelized on GPUs and implemented in-situ as part of *PICongPU*.

The physics of this plugins was successfully implemented, tested and verified to agree with an initial python implementation, which again was verified using analytical CTR theory, with an average error of less than 1%. Additionally the plugin was benchmarked, resulting in typical time to solutions for complete transition radiation spectra on the scale of several minutes.

The *CTR plugin* was then used in several Laser-wakefield accelerator (LWFA) simulations, with self-injected and down-ramp injected electrons respectively. Mimicking the hypothetical placement of successive transition radiaton foils along the LWFA interaction length, the *CTR plugin* was used multiple times for observing how the electron bunch evolution leads to the characteristic features of transition radiation spectra.

This new tool is a synthetic diagnostic, which enables direct comparison of experimentally measured transition radiation data to simulations. In future experiments this can provide insight into LWFA longitudinal electron pulse profiles on the fs-scale, required for future compact LWFA-driven free-electron laser applications.

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1 Introduction

Conventional radio frequency based electron accelerators can accelerate electrons to energies from MeV and GeV only over long distances due to their relatively low accelerating electric field gradients $\propto 10$ MV/m. An alternative to these accelerators are plasma based accelerators, which can achieve ~ 1000 times higher acceleration fields. One way to accelerate electrons within a plasma, is to use laser pulses to drive plasma waves which can trap and accelerate electrons [2–4]. The electron bunches have a small transversal and longitudinal extent [5–9]. These LWFA (laser wakefield accelerators) can become compact alternatives to radio frequency based accelerators. At the moment they are utilized e.g. as drivers of high yield x-ray sources [10, 11]. It is also foreseen to drive future free-electron lasers with LWFA [12, 13].

In order to apply these electron bunches to a specific use case, it is important to determine their properties in terms of spatial extent, divergence and energy spread [7]. Radiation based diagnostic tools for accelerated electron bunches are synchrotron radiation, Thomson backscatter radiation, betatron radiation and transition radiation [7]. This bachelor thesis focuses on transition radiation, which is caused by a relativistic, charged particle transiting from one medium to another medium with a different dielectric constant and depends on the spatial and momentum distribution of the electron bunch [14]. Thus it is an important tool to analyze the spatial and momentum characteristics of electron bunches [1, 15–17]. Since the described LWFA operate in a highly nonlinear regime, one needs numerical

Figure 1.1: Cross-section output of the electron density on the axis of laser propagation from 3D Particle-in-Cell simulation (*Illumination*) showing a snapshot of a laser-generated plasma. The laser pulse has excited a comoving, nonlinear charge-density wave (“bubble”) in the plasma. This structure provides a high, on axis electric field $E_z(z)$ (green) on the order of TV/m for electron acceleration. Taken from [1].

1 Introduction

methods to understand the physics behind these accelerators [18]. One tool to simulate plasmas is *PIConGPU* [19], a particle-in-cell code, which solves the relativistic Maxwell equations for a given setup. In this bachelor thesis an in-situ plugin, the *CTR plugin*, is created for calculating the transition radiation generated in simulations of laser plasma accelerators. An advantage of an in-situ plugin is, that one does not have to load the simulation data in a post-processing program. The transition radiation is dependent on the space and the momentum of the particle. When using 32 bit floating point numbers to store a bunch containing 10^{10} particles, one has to store $6 \times 32 \text{ bit} \times 10^{10} \approx 2 \text{ Tb}$ and load this into an program. An in-situ plugin allows for a more efficient calculation, since the required data is already on the computing device.

2 Theory of transition radiation and LWFA's

2.1 Transition radiation from a single electron

In general transition radiation is created by relativistic, charged particles moving from one medium to another medium with a different electric permittivity ϵ_r . In order to describe transition radiation, first the focus of this section will be set onto the transition radiation of a single relativistic electron passing through a metal foil into vacuum. This foil has an infinite extent and it is perfectly conducting.

The electron has a Lorentz contracted Coulomb field, since the electron is moving with a relativistic velocity as shown in [20]. This means, that the Coulomb field is not radially symmetric, but its envelope has an opening angle $\propto 1/\gamma_e$ in the plane perpendicular to the electrons direction of motion and it is directly related to the electrons energy $E = \gamma_e mc^2$

Figure 2.1: (a) shows the coordinate-system used in this thesis. \vec{r} is the position vector and \vec{p} the momentum vector of the electron. ϕ and θ are the polar and azimuth angle of \vec{p} with respect to the main coordinate-system. \vec{R} represents the observation vector in the x - z plane with the azimuth angle θ [14]. The metal foil is in the x - y plane. (b) shows the Lorentz contracted Coulomb field of the electron leaving the metal foil and the corresponding wavelength with λ_1 being emitted closer than $\lambda_2 > \lambda_1$ to the point of transit [7].

Figure 2.2: Ginzburg-Frank formula eq. (2.1) shown for different electron momenta. The vertical line depicts the angle $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$.

[21]. As long as the electron is within the metal foil the Coulomb field is shielded from the electrons around it. But as soon as it is leaving the foil, the Coulomb field is acting on the electrons on the surface of the foil and is inducing a radial current or polarization waves (in a dielectric). The metal electrons at a distance ρ are perturbed over a longitudinal extent $\sim \rho/\gamma_e$. This leads to electromagnetic waves with the wavelength λ being emitted at the distance $\lambda\gamma_e$ from the point of transit. Hence smaller wavelengths are emitted closer to the electron, longer wavelengths further away from the electron as shown in fig. 2.1b.

Another way of describing the transition radiation is with the help of an image charge in the conducting metal foil [22]. If the electron transits the metal foil at the time $t = 0$, the previously shielded Coulomb field expands into the vacuum. It connects with the electric field from the image charge, because electric field lines terminate only at charges. The electric field is expanding with the speed of light to a sphere with the radius $r = ct$ from the point of transit and it creates an electromagnetic shock front [7]. The electromagnetic shock front is infinitesimally thin and the source of the transition radiation.

The transition radiation for the azimuth angle θ shown in fig. 2.1a created by an electron passing through the foil in the solid angle $d\Omega$ with the frequency $d\omega$ is described by the Ginzburg-Frank formula [14]

$$\frac{d^2W_e}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{r_e m_e c}{\pi^2} \frac{\beta^2 \sin^2 \theta}{(1 - \beta^2 \cos^2 \theta)^2} \quad (2.1)$$

with the classical electron radius $r_e = e^2/(4\pi\epsilon_0 m_e c^2)$ and the normalized electron velocity $\beta = v/c$. First one can see, that the equation only depends on θ of the solid angle $d\Omega = \sin\theta d\theta d\phi$. This not only leads to a rotational symmetry of the transition, but also to radially polarization of the radiation. The maximum of the angular distribution from the transition radiation is located at $\theta \simeq 1/\gamma_e = \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$. Figure 2.2a shows the transition

Figure 2.3: (a) shows the radial symmetry of eq. (2.1) for an electron with $\gamma_e = 10$ as a slice of the radiation for $\phi = 0$. (b) shows the rotational symmetry as a heatmap with the polar angle ϕ over the azimuth angle θ .

radiation profile of an electron with the Lorentz factor $\gamma_e = 100$ and fig. 2.2b for an electron with $\gamma_e = 10$. The vertical line denotes the expected maximum at $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$, which fits the maximum of the radiation curves. If one compares both figures, it is also clear, that the intensity is increasing with an increasing electron velocity and the radiation cone becomes smaller with higher velocities. One can calculate the energy dependency, by integrating eq. (2.1) over the solid angle Ω for $\gamma_e \gg 1$, resulting in the spectral power:

$$\frac{dW_e}{d\omega} = \frac{2r_e m_e c}{\pi} \ln(\gamma_e) \quad (2.2)$$

In fig. 2.3a one can see the axial symmetry $W(\theta) = W(-\theta)$, which is equal to the independence of ϕ as shown in fig. 2.3b. One can also see the reflected transition radiation at the radiation angles $\theta = (\pi - 1/\gamma)$ and $\theta = (-\pi + 1/\gamma)$.

Also important to notice is, that the formula does not depend on the frequency $\omega = 2\pi c/\lambda$. In a real scenario one will get a cutoff for low as well as high frequencies. The low-frequency cutoff is caused by the physical dimensions of the metal foil. As discussed earlier, longer wavelengths are created further away from the point of transit. Since no real physical setup can implement an infinite surface area, this leads to the low-frequency cutoff. The high-frequency cutoff on the other hand is due to the plasma-frequency $\omega_p = \sqrt{n_e e^2 / m_e \epsilon_0}$ of the metal foil. If the radiated frequency is larger than the critical frequency $\omega_{crit} = \gamma_e \omega_p$, the foil will become transparent to the passing electrons electric field. This leads to the foil becoming transparent for the Coulomb-field of the electron and the electric permittivity of the foil becomes equal to the vacuum permittivity. Thus there is no higher frequency emitted than ω_{crit} . For solid foils ω_{crit} is usually in the extreme ultraviolet to soft x-ray range, but it may be lower for plasma-vacuum transition [7].

2.2 Transition radiation from multiple electrons

The preceding section only shows the transition radiation created by a single electron. This section will focus on a more general formalism of transition radiation created by multiple electrons. For the derivation we will assume a plasma vacuum interface in the x-y plane, where the plasma is uniformly distributed until $z < 0$ and the vacuum starts at $z > 0$. The coordinate system used is depicted in fig. 2.1a. The emitted radiation fields can be calculated by solving the following combined Maxwell equation [14]:

$$(c^2 \nabla^2 - \partial_t^2) \vec{E} = 4\pi \partial_t (\vec{J}_b + \vec{J}_p) + 4\pi c^2 \nabla (\rho_b + \rho_p) \quad (2.3)$$

where \vec{J}_b and \vec{J}_p are the currents of the electron bunch and the plasma, ρ_b and ρ_p the densities, respectively, and \vec{E} is the electric field. One can solve the equation as shown in [14] using the Poisson equation $\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = 4\pi (\rho_b + \rho_p)$ and the continuity equation $\partial_t \rho = -\nabla \cdot \vec{J}$. For better readability the electric field \vec{E} created by a single electron is decomposed in a part parallel to the bunch's direction of propagation and a perpendicular part:

$$\mathcal{E}_{\parallel} = \frac{u \cos \psi \left[u \sin \psi \cos \phi - (1 + u^2)^{1/2} \sin \theta \right]}{\mathcal{N}(\theta, u, \psi, \phi)} \quad (2.4)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{\perp} = \frac{u^2 \cos \psi \sin \psi \sin \phi \cos \theta}{\mathcal{N}(\theta, u, \psi, \phi)} \quad (2.5)$$

With the denominator given by:

$$\mathcal{N}(\theta, u, \psi, \phi) = \left[(1 + u^2)^{1/2} - u \sin \psi \cos \phi \sin \theta \right]^2 - u^2 \cos^2 \psi \cos^2 \theta \quad (2.6)$$

$u = p/m_e c = \gamma_e \beta$ is the normalized momentum, ψ and ϕ the azimuth and polar angle of the electrons momentum vector with respect to the foil normal and θ the angle of the detector as shown in fig. 2.1a. One can already see, that the perpendicular electric field eq. (2.5) vanishes for a perfectly collimated electron bunch, since all momentum angles ψ are 0. For this setup the radiation will be radially polarized. In a more general case with a tilted electron bunch the transition radiation is elliptically polarized [7]. If one integrates over the according Poynting vector for eq. (2.4) and eq. (2.5), one obtains the radiated energy per frequency $d\omega$ and solid angle $d\Omega$:

$$\frac{d^2 W}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{e^2 N_e}{(4\pi \epsilon_0) \pi^2 c} \left\{ \left[\int d^3 \vec{p} g (\mathcal{E}_{\parallel}^2 + \mathcal{E}_{\perp}^2) \right] + (N_e - 1) \left[\left| \int d^3 \vec{p} g \mathcal{E}_{\parallel} F \right|^2 + \left| \int d^3 \vec{p} g \mathcal{E}_{\perp} F \right|^2 \right] \right\} \quad (2.7)$$

where $g(\vec{p})$ is the normalized momentum distribution of the electron bunch $\int d^3 \vec{p} g(\vec{p}) = 1$ and F the normalized spatial form factor, which manages the phase properties of the single electrons and is defined by:

$$F = \frac{1}{g(\vec{p})} \int d^2 \vec{r}_{\perp} e^{-i \vec{k}_{\perp} \cdot \vec{r}_{\perp}} \int dz e^{-iz(\omega - \vec{k}_{\perp} \cdot \vec{v}_{\perp})/v_z} h(\vec{r}, \vec{p}) \quad (2.8)$$

Figure 2.4: Incoherent part of transition radiation at $\omega = 100$ MHz, one graph has a perfectly collimated electron bunch with a Gaussian distributed divergence with the standard deviation $\sigma_\Psi = 0$ mrad and another bunch with $\sigma_\Psi = 0.02$ mrad. Both bunches consist of $N_e = 1000$ electrons with $\gamma_e = 100$. The polar observation angle ϕ is 0.

Equation (2.7) can be separated in an incoherent part W_{ITR} , which is on the left-hand side and the coherent W_{CTR} part on the right-hand side as follows:

$$\frac{d^2W_{ITR}}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{e^2 N_e}{(4\pi\epsilon_0)\pi^2 c} \int d^3\vec{p} g(\mathcal{E}_\parallel^2 + \mathcal{E}_\perp^2) \propto N_e \quad (2.9)$$

$$\frac{d^2W_{CTR}}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{e^2 N_e(N_e - 1)}{(4\pi\epsilon_0)\pi^2 c} \left[\left| \int d^3\vec{p} g \mathcal{E}_\parallel F \right|^2 + \left| \int d^3\vec{p} g \mathcal{E}_\perp F \right|^2 \right] \propto N_e^2 \quad (2.10)$$

First we focus on the incoherent part of eq. (2.7). In fig. 2.4 the incoherent part is plotted for two monochromatic electron bunches, where one is collimated and the other one has a divergence. Both bunches have a Gaussian spatial distribution. The divergence leads to a detectable radiation at $\theta = 0$, but also to a decrease in the maximum spectral power. One can also see, that the maximum is still close to the angle $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$. If one compares the maximum intensity with fig. 2.2a, one can also see, that it is ~ 1000 times higher, which is equal to the amount of electrons in this simulation.

The incoherent part of the radiation becomes important in real physical experiments, when the observed wavelength $\lambda = 2\pi c/\omega$ is small compared to the bunch length, since the wavelengths are not coherently superimposed and the form factor (eq. (2.8)) approaches 0. If the detected wavelength becomes too small, the phase differences between the electrons are large. But if one observes longer wavelengths, which are equal to smaller frequencies ω , phase differences between electrons are short and radiation is adding up coherently. This

Figure 2.5: Incoherent and coherent parts of transition radiation (eq. (2.9) and eq. (2.10)) and their effect to the total radiation with a changing frequency $\omega = 2\pi c/\lambda$ for an electron bunch with $N_e = 1000$ electrons with a velocity $\gamma_e = 100$ calculated at the angles $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$ and $\phi = 0$.

leads to a scaling $\propto N_e^2$ for the coherent part, which is therefore the dominant transition radiation signal in an experiment.

Figure 2.5 shows the scaling of the radiated spectrum with observed frequency ω . For this calculation, an electron bunch with $N_e = 1000$ particles was assumed with a Gaussian spatial distribution in the direction of motion with the standard deviation $\sigma_z = 3 \mu\text{m}$. The detected total energy $W_{ITR} + W_{OTR}$ decreases rapidly, as soon as the detected frequency reaches $\omega \simeq 10^{14} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is equal to $\lambda \simeq 20 \mu\text{m}$. This length is equal to the specific bunch length following from $\sigma_z = 3 \mu\text{m}$. As expected, the coherent part of the transition radiation was not noticeable at low frequencies, it dominates the high-frequency spectrum, where the coherent part is just contributing noise. Due to the proportionality of the coherent and incoherent part of the transition radiation with $\propto N_e^2$ and $\propto N_e$, respectively, one can identify the amount of particles in the electron bunch in fig. 2.5 as well. If one divides the intensity of the higher plateau with the intensity of the lower plateau, one obtains $2 \times 10^{-28} \text{ Js} / 2 \times 10^{-31} \text{ Js} = 10^3 = 1000$ which is the amount of electrons. This shows how important the radiation spectrum is for getting information on the bunch shape and the bunch charge.

If the electron bunch does not hit the foil perpendicularly, the radiation will obviously not look as symmetric, as discussed in this chapter and ref. [17]. Section 4.2 will also consider a bunch impacting the surface at an angle $\psi = \pi/4$. In a realistic scenario, one also has to consider, that the surface will not be infinite in transverse extent, which leads to diffraction effects in the transition radiation, which are further discussed in [14].

2.3 Laser wakefield accelerators

Conventional radio-frequency based accelerators are limited in acceleration gradient ~ 100 MV/m due to the material breakdown at the walls. This leads to them being very large and expensive. Hence laser plasma based accelerators were researched, which can provide electric fields ~ 96 GV/m [2], which is ~ 1000 times higher. The idea of a plasma accelerators was first published in 1979 [23]. In this section these acceleration methods will be explained.

In order to obtain such an accelerator, one needs a plasma and a laser. First the effect of a laser on a single electron is explained. A laser can be described as an electromagnetic wave with the electric field $\vec{E} = -\partial_t \vec{A}/c$ and the magnetic field $\vec{B} = \nabla \times \vec{A}$ [2]. The normalized vector potential of the laser's field is $\vec{a} = e\vec{A}/m_e c^2$. This electric field exerts a ponderomotive force

$$\vec{F}_p = -m_e c^2 \nabla (a^2/2) \quad (2.11)$$

on the plasma electrons, which is directed along the laser's intensity gradient. The peak amplitude a_0 of the normalized field of a laser is $a_0^2 = (e\lambda/m_e c^2)^2 (2/\pi c) I_0$ with the peak laser intensity I_0 given by the power $P = \pi r_0^2 I_0/2$ [2]. One has to note that the laser frequency ω has to be larger than the plasma frequency $\omega > \omega_p$, which is given by $\omega_p = \sqrt{n_e e^2/m_e \epsilon_0}$, so that it is not reflected from the plasma. Since the common lasers, which are capable of reaching the high energies while maintaining a short pulse duration, are near-infrared lasers and operate at $\sim 0.8 \mu\text{m}$, the maximum density is given by $n_e < 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

The laser now creates a charge separation in the plasma, pushing electrons away transversely like a snow plow, creating a spherical, almost electron free bubble behind the laser. The longitudinal electric field in this bubble has an accelerating effect for electrons in the back of the bubble and a decelerating effect for electrons in the front. The transverse electric field in the bubble pulls the electrons back to the laser propagation axis. This charge separation creates their own electric field, which acts accelerating on the longitudinal axis and focusing on the transverse axis. The maximum accelerating field is given by

$$E_0 = m_e \omega_p c / e \quad (2.12)$$

Different laser intensities lead to different regimes in the laser plasma interaction. If the laser intensity $a_0 < 1$, the laser plasma interactions are linear and the laser creates sinusoidal density waves in the plasma. These can be described with cold fluid equations. If $a_0 \geq 1$, the laser plasma interactions become non linear and one needs numerical methods to describe them. The waves create nonsinusoidal features like steepened wave fronts or lengthened wake periods, that are caused by the relativistic mass increase of the driven plasma electrons. The waves can also break in the non linear regime [18].

As soon as $a_0 \gtrsim 3$, the laser is strong enough to completely evacuate electrons from the first wake and cause a spherical cavity just filled with ions behind the laser. This regime is called the bubble-regime. The bubble diameter depends on the plasma wavelength $\lambda_p = 2\pi c/\omega_p$. Electrons are injected into the bubble and can be accelerated in the strong electric field at the back of the bubble. Today most LWFA's operate in this regime. The electrons are quasimonoenergetic, because they are localized in space and time before the

Figure 2.6: Shows the electron density of the bunch created with self-injection with a greyscale. The darker an area is, the more electrons are in the area. The x-axis is the axis of the propagation direction (z), the y-axis is x in fig. 2.1a. Both are denoted in μm . Note that the frame is moving with the speed of light along the laser. (This simulation will be further discussed in section 5.1, but general parameters are the density $n_e = 5.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$, the intensity $a_0 = 5.0$ and the pulse length $\sigma = 4.25 \text{ fs}$)

injection, which leads to them observing the same acceleration field. They also have a small transverse emittance caused by the strong focusing fields in the bubble and a short bunch duration.

Figure 2.6 shows how a laser accelerates a self injected electron bunch in a plasma. It is a simulation made with *PIConGPU* and will be explained thoroughly in section 5.1. First the laser enters the plasma, creating a wave by pushing electrons away transversely. If the plasma density increases and the laser propagates in the plasma, electrons form a bubble. After further propagation the electron density at the border of the bubbles increase, the bubbles diameter decreases due to the overall increase in plasma density and at $t = 1.3 \text{ ps}$ the density is high enough and the electric field in the bubble is strong enough to start injecting electrons from the plasma wake. At $t = 3.8 \text{ ps}$ one can clearly see the injected electrons. These are focused by the transverse electric field and accelerated by the longitudinal electric field on the back-side of the bubble. The electrons then get ejected from the plasma with a high energy. One can see one problem with LWFA in this figure, which is the high divergence of the electron beam in the vacuum after ejection.

Another injection method is the downramp injection [24]. Here one uses a laser $a_0 \gtrsim 1$ to create a bubble in the density n_e with the diameter $\lambda_p \propto 1/\sqrt{n_e}$. Now one decreases the the density to $n'_e < n_e$ rapidly, i.e. within 1-2 plasma periods, which leads to an increase of the bubble size. Electrons, which used to be in the back of the bubble are now directly

injected into the bigger bubble and they get accelerated by the electric field. Instead of using a laser to create the wake in the plasma, one can also use an externally generated electron or positron beam, because these also interact electromagnetically with the plasma electrons. This is called PWFA (plasma wakefield acceleration) [25].

3 Implementation of coherent transition radiation into PIConGPU

3.1 The particle-in-cell code PIConGPU

PIConGPU is a particle-in-cell (PIC) code, which is used for simulating plasmas [19, 26]. A particle-in-cell code uses particles, represented by a few macro-particles, as well as discretized electric and magnetic fields for the simulation [27]. A macro-particle represents an ensemble of physical particles, such as electrons or ions. These move through the simulation box following the Maxwell-equations. The electric and magnetic field of the simulation on the other hand are discretized on a grid in the simulation box. The cells of the grid are further grouped to super-cells, which contain all particles and the data for all fields in this spatial subdomain. This allows more efficient field calculation. Macro-particles are required for efficient plasma calculation, since one could not simulate a plasma with todays technology by looking at each particle one by one. These macro-particles have e.g. a position distribution, a single momentum, which is necessary so that the macro-particle, does not drift apart, and a weighting, which is equal to the amount of particles the macro-particle represents.

The particle-in-cell algorithm is sketched in fig. 3.1 in the circular flow chart, where each step updates variables, which are used by a following step to calculate a new variable. *PIConGPU* also behaves physically correct in the relativistic regime, e.g. respecting relativistic mass changes of particles, which is important for plasma physics scenarios in the relativistic regime. The starting conditions of the simulation will also be left out for simplicity.

Figure 3.1: Schematic visualization of the 4 steps of the particle-in-cell algorithm

The PIC code is first taking the electric and magnetic field of the grid and computes the Lorentz force acting on the particles, as shown in the blue box. Then it takes this force to solve the equations of motion (green box). These two steps strongly depend on each other, but are still two separate steps. Hence they have their own boxes in the flow chart. They are called *particle push* since they are moving the particles. There are multiple methods to calculate the *particle push* efficiently; which are called particle pushers. Subsequently *PIConGPU* takes the velocities and charges of the particles to calculate the currents (red box) and finally it calculates the electric field using Ampere's and Faraday's law (yellow box). These 2 steps can be calculated with different algorithms again, like the particle pusher. A full cycle in fig. 3.1 equals a time-step in the simulation.

The whole simulation box in *PIConGPU* is divided in super-cells, which are split between the different GPUs. Every super-cell contains information about the electric and magnetic fields, and about the particles and induced currents in the super-cell. A super-cell only has limited information about the neighboring super-cells. To reduce performance expensive communication over the network between different GPUs, each super-cell also contains guarding cells, which are overlapping with the neighboring super-cells.

Every time-step a *plugin controller* is called, starting plugins which are user determined. These plugins have access to the particle and field information and are used for e.g. calculating energy histograms, phase space images or the transition radiation with the *CTR plugin*.

3.2 Numerical implementation of the CTR plugin

In order to implement eq. (2.7) into *PIConGPU*, the equation was adapted for performance reasons. Solving integrals would require a lot of computing power, but it is not required in the case of the *CTR plugin*. The momentum distribution in PIC simulations is discrete and not continuous. A macro-particle's spatial distribution is represented by a density profile in the PIC code. But since this density profile is small compared to the characteristic dimensions for the transition radiation, it is assumed that it is discrete as well. Thus

both are assumed to be sums of Dirac delta functions $\delta(x) = \begin{cases} +\infty, & x = 0 \\ 0, & x \neq 0 \end{cases}$. The position distribution looks like

$$f(\vec{r}) = \frac{\delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_0) + \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_1) + \dots + \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_{N_e-1}) + \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_{N_e})}{N_e} \quad (3.1)$$

with \vec{r}_i being the position of the i th electron. The momentum distribution $g(\vec{p})$ is equivalent but with \vec{p}_i instead of \vec{r}_i . The sum of the delta functions is divided by the number of electrons N_e due to the normalization of the distribution $\int d\vec{r} f(\vec{r}) = 1$. This transforms the integrals over the distribution functions into sums over all particles.

$$\int d\vec{r} f(\vec{r}) \rightarrow \sum_{\text{real particles}} \frac{1}{N_e} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\int d\vec{p} g(\vec{p}) \rightarrow \sum_{\text{real particles}} \frac{1}{N_e} \quad (3.3)$$

3 Implementation of coherent transition radiation into *PIConGPU*

As discussed in the previous section, *PIConGPU* is not simulating single particles, but macro-particles, which are representing an ensemble of the same particle species. Thus the sums transform as follows:

$$\sum_{\text{real particles}} \frac{1}{N_e} \rightarrow \widetilde{\sum} \frac{w_i}{N_e} \quad (3.4)$$

For simplicity the sum over all macro-particles with the index i is shortened to $\widetilde{\sum}$. The weighting of the i th macro-particle is w_i representing the amount of particles in the macro-particle. The final implemented incoherent and coherent parts of the transition radiation from eq. (2.7) look like

$$\frac{d^2 W_{ITR}}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{e^2}{(4\pi\epsilon_0)\pi^2 c} \widetilde{\sum} \left(w_i (\mathcal{E}_{i,\parallel}^2 + \mathcal{E}_{i,\perp}^2) \right) \quad (3.5)$$

$$\frac{d^2 W_{CTR}}{d\omega d\Omega} = \frac{e^2}{(4\pi\epsilon_0)\pi^2 c} \frac{N_e - 1}{N_e} \left(\left| \widetilde{\sum} w_i \mathcal{E}_{i,\parallel} F_i \right|^2 + \left| \widetilde{\sum} w_i \mathcal{E}_{i,\perp} F_i \right|^2 \right) \quad (3.6)$$

It is important to note, that the scaling with N_e and N_e^2 now does not look as obvious as in eq. (2.7), but it is still obtained due to weightings in the sums. There is also the fraction $(N_e - 1)/N_e$, which approximates to 1 for large N_e expected in realistic physical simulations. But since it is easier to prove the implementation for setups with less particles, it is kept.

Right now the plugin assumes all real particles of a macro-particle to be at the same position. Thus a macro-particle emits radiation completely coherently, which opposes the real case, where 2 particles in a bunch always have a phase difference to each other, leading to incoherent radiation. Ref. [28] examines how to treat the this phase differences of real particles inside a macro-particle in PIC codes. But these phase-differences matter for lengths in the scale of the size of the cells in the PIC simulation, which is much smaller than the bunch length. Equation (2.7) is already split into a momentum dependent incoherent part and a momentum and space dependent coherent part. The inner macro-particle form factor is important for the spatial distribution of the particles, thus only for the coherent part of the transition radiation. Since the coherent part of the transition radiation at the scale of the cell-size is only a noise term, the inner macro-particle form factor is negligible for calculating the transition radiation of electron bunches in PIC codes.

Figure 3.2 shows, how the eq. (3.5) and eq. (3.6) are implemented in *PIConGPU*. The base program is parallelized on CPUs and GPUs and basically the CPUs are used for file output tasks, whereas the GPUs are used for calculating performance intensive tasks. The *plugin controller* of *PIConGPU* is calling the *CTR plugin*, as well as all other plugins, at user defined time steps. The *CTR Controller*, which is equal to the CPU side of the plugin, is now preparing the electron data from the simulation on the GPU like executing a γ_e -filter, which excludes particles below a certain γ_e . This is done to reduce calculation times, because only relativistic electrons contribute to the transition radiation. It is also similar to physical experiments, where lower energy electrons get blocked by the foil. Electrons with a lower energy also have a higher divergence (section 2.1), meaning their radiation gets blocked by the aperture of the spectrometer. This is called an acceptance angle. The controller is parallelizing the tasks over the observer angles ϕ and θ (fig. 2.1a) and starts

Figure 3.2: Diagram showing CPU and GPU operations when using the Transition Radiation Kernel in *PIConGPU*. [29]

the kernels for all observers.

The *CTR plugin* is based on the *radiation plugin* ([29], [30]). The flow chart of the *CTR Kernel*, which is the parallelized code running on the GPU, is shown in fig. 3.3. The master thread gets a frame of particles, which is equal to a list of macro-particles in a super-cell, and shares it with all other threads. After a synchronization, it will be checked, whether the frame is valid, and then everything from eq. (3.5) and eq. (3.6) which is not influenced by the detected frequency ω will be calculated. After a synchronization, it will be checked, whether the frame is valid and the normalized energies of eq. (3.5) and eq. (3.6) will be calculated. Most of the form factor will be calculated in this step as well, since the exponent in eq. (2.8) is completely linearly proportional to $k = \omega/c$. Thus one can calculate the exponent of the form factor without the frequency here and save computation time in the next step. These calculations are done for all particles in the current frame. The next step is a loop over all frequencies, to calculate the coherent form factor, which just means taking the exponential function of the previously calculated exponent times ω . There is a maximum amount of frequencies, that can be handled in parallel, which is given by the maximum amount of CUDA threads.

When all threads are finished and their frequencies have been handled, the kernel first checks, whether there are more frequencies ω , which have to be calculated. After everything is computed for all frequencies, the *CTR Kernel* goes to the beginning of the cycle again and loads a new frame of particles, until the transition radiation is calculated for all particle

CTR Analyzer → Kernel

Figure 3.3: Flow chart from the kernel of the Transition Radiation plugin. Note that $(\ln F/\omega)$ is equal to the frequency independent part of the exponent of the form factor. [29]

Figure 3.4: (a) shows the calculation time of the same simulation calculated with *Nvidia P100*, *Nvidia K80* and *Nvidia K20*. (b) shows the calculation time with the same simulation with a changing amount of macro-particles per GPU on *Nvidia K80*.

frames. Finally all computed values get transferred to the CPU, where the absolute square of the sum of eq. (3.6) gets calculated for all detected frequencies and solid angles. The last step is transferring the unit of this transition radiation from PIConGPU internal units into SI units and saving it with the other simulation output.

3.3 Benchmark of the CTR plugin

In this section a brief benchmark is provided for the *CTR plugin* to give a sense of its performance.

First the simulation time for different GPUs (*Nvidia P100*, *Nvidia K80* and *Nvidia K20*) on the *hemera*-cluster is examined. The tilted bunch simulation from section 4.2 was taken to make sure that no optimization effects appear for the longitudinal parts of eq. (3.5) and eq. (3.6). This simulation is run with $\propto 4 \times 10^6$ macro-particles per GPU. The *CTR plugin* calculates the transition radiation for $N_\omega = 256$ different frequencies and $N_\theta \times N_\phi = 256 \times 32 = 8192$ different observation angles. Thus the radiation intensity is calculated $N_\omega \times N_\theta \times N_\phi \simeq 2 \times 10^6$ times. The resulting calculation times are shown in fig. 3.4a. The *Nvidia P100* calculate the same coherent transition radiation \propto four times faster than the *Nvidia K80* and \propto five times faster than the *Nvidia K20*. To have a better understanding of the impact from different steps of fig. 3.2 on the plugin performance, table 3.1 was created. One can see that the Kernel run still the fastest on the *Nvidia P100*. But the largest impact on the plugin performance comes from the CPU side. This is caused

3 Implementation of coherent transition radiation into PIConGPU

GPU	<i>Nvidia P100</i>	<i>Nvidia K80</i>	<i>Nvidia K20</i>
Total computation time [s]	61.56	208.6	246.1
Computation time on GPU [s]	0.9	1.9	1.9
GPU time / total time [%]	1.5×10^{-2}	8.9×10^{-5}	7.6×10^{-5}
Comput. time per obs. angle & part. [s]	1.9×10^{-9}	6.4×10^{-9}	7.5×10^{-9}

Table 3.1: Shows the real duration of the kernel for the *CTR plugin* benchmark from fig. 3.4a and the amount of calculation time of the kernel relative to the total plugin duration. Additionally it shows the computation time per observation angle θ and ϕ , calculated frequency ω and macro-particle.

by the not-parallelized sum with the absolute squares from eq. (3.6). These calculations have to happen on the CPU instead of the GPUs, since a GPU only contains informations about the particles it contains and $|\sum_{\text{particles}} x|^2 \neq \sum_{\text{particles}} |x|^2$. The time the *CTR plugin* needs to calculate the transition radiation for one frequency in one observation direction per macro-particle, approximated with the help of the total computation time and the used radiation resolution, is also shown in table 3.1.

Figure 3.4b shows the required amount of calculation time for the same simulation setup, with a higher resolution for the observed azimuth angle $N_\theta = 512$, leading a total amount $\propto 4 \times 10^6$ transition radiation values being calculated. It also shows a linear fit through the measured computation times.

One has to note, that these calculation times depend highly on N_ω , N_θ and N_ϕ . A comparison with fig. 3.4a and fig. 3.4b suggests, that the calculation time scales linearly with N_θ . Thus it also scales linearly with N_ϕ since the plugin itself handles both observation angles in the same manner. Hence one can increase the performance of this plugin by e.g. looking only at the spectrum in a rotational symmetric setup and setting N_ϕ to a small number. The performance can further be increased by adjusting the γ_e filter and using multiple GPUs. Thus the performance of the *CTR plugin* is considerably faster than loading $\propto 100$ GB – TB of particle data into an external program. Furthermore, the time increase caused by the *CTR plugin* only slightly effects the overall simulation time since the plugin does not need to its results for every PIC-iteration.

4 Validating the PIC implementation

This chapter will use different methods to validate the physical results of the *CTR plugin*. The difference Δ_W between both methods is given by taking the mean, absolute difference of both methods for all angles θ . The relative difference $\Delta_{W,rel.}$ is the absolute difference Δ_W divided by the mean maximum of the spectral power calculated by the PIC plugin and the verification code. Since this will lead to very small relative differences, the standard deviation is given as well. Δ_W^{max} is the maximal difference between both calculation methods and $\Delta_{W,rel.}^{max}$ is the maximum from the absolute difference relative to the mean intensity at the maximums location.

4.1 Validation with a single electron

To check for a physically correct behavior of the *CTR plugin*, a single electron setup is useful, since this is comparable to analytic descriptions. The Ginzburg Frank formula describes this setup as elaborated earlier and will be used to compare with the simulation outcome. This setup is obviously not useful for checking the coherent part of transition radiation, since coherence effects require phase differences, which are not given with a single electron. Also the coherent part in eq. (3.6) is multiplied with $N_e - 1$. Hence the sum is omitted.

The simulation is based on the *Single Particle Test* example setup of *PICongPU*. Because there is no need for additional electrical or magnetic fields, these were neglected from the simulation. Also the momentum of the electron was set to be exactly on the y-axis with an the Lorentz factor of $\gamma_e = 100$.

In fig. 4.1a one can compare the output of the PIC simulation with the theoretical Ginzburg-Frank formula eq. (2.1). The values are compared to each other in fig. 4.1b. The PIC simulation output is very close to the theoretical expectation. The average absolute difference between the PIC simulation and the Ginzburg Frank formula is $\Delta_W = (8.4 \pm 45.1) \times 10^{-39}$ Js. The relative difference is $\Delta_{W,rel.} = (4.3 \pm 23.1) \times 10^{-3}$ %. The maximum absolute difference is $\Delta_W^{max} = 7.1 \times 10^{-37}$ Js, which is $\Delta_{W,rel.}^{max} = 5.0$ % relative to the local intensity average.

The vertical line in fig. 4.1a is plotted at $\theta = 0.01$ rad, which is equal to $1/\gamma_e$. The transition radiation is being detected at the polar angle $\phi = 0$ rad. Thus one gets the maximum transition radiation intensity at the azimuth angle $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$.

If the scope of θ is increased from $\theta \in [0, \pi/8]$ to $\theta \in [-\pi, \pi]$, there are 4 peaks with the same amount of intensity, which is also predicted by eq. (2.1) and shown in fig. 4.2a. The mean absolute difference between the PIC code and the Ginzburg-Frank formula is $\Delta_W = (2.6 \pm 31.3) \times 10^{-39}$ Js, the relative difference is $\Delta_{W,rel.} = (1.3 \pm 16.2) \times 10^{-3}$ %.

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Figure 4.1: Result of a PIC Simulation for one electron with $\gamma_e = 100$ and the according solution of the Ginzburg Frank equation. The polar angle is fixed at $\phi = 0$ rad and the detected frequency is: $\omega = 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$. (a) shows the angular distribution over θ and (b) shows the difference between both methods.

Figure 4.2: Radial symmetry of the PIC simulation for an electron with $\gamma_e = 100$. (a) shows a slice of the angular radiation distribution at $\phi = 0$ rad at the frequency $\omega = 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$, (b) shows the angular radiation distribution depending on both spherical angles as a heatmap with the same detected frequency.

This difference is small compared to the deviation of fig. 4.1b due to the low radiation intensity transversal to the electrons direction of motion. The maximal absolute difference is $\Delta_W^{max} = 6.7 \times 10^{-37}$ Js, which is relative to the local intensity $\Delta_{W,rel.}^{max} = 1.1\%$. The peak at $\theta = -1/\gamma_e$ can be explained by the rotational symmetry of our setup. The peaks at $\theta = (\pi - 1/\gamma_e)$ and $\theta = (-\pi + 1/\gamma_e)$ are reflected peaks of radiation. One can understand these peaks by the assumption of the transition radiation formula, that the metal foil is infinitely thin, thus the radiation of the metal foil electrons is emitted on both sides of the metal foil.

Figure 4.2b shows the intensity heatmap of this simulation, where the detectors are setup to detect at the angles $\theta \in [0, \pi/8]$ on the x-axis and $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$ on the y-axis. One can already see the rotational symmetry of the simulation output, which is expected, since a single electron passing through the metal foil perpendicularly has no rotational asymmetry. This symmetry is explored more accurately by calculating the standard deviation of the radiation at a fixed $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$ over all angles ϕ . This error is likely caused by the numerical precision of floating point numbers and thus negligible.

Another important feature of the Ginzburg Frank intensity distribution is the minimum at $\theta = 0$ rad, which is also reproduced in this simulation.

Overall the deviations from the PIC simulation to the Ginzburg Frank formula eq. (2.1) are very small $\propto 2 \times 10^{-3}\%$. This is caused by the numerical error through floating point precision. Thus the PIC simulation agrees very well with section 2.1.

4.2 Validation with multiple electrons

For further verification of the implemented transition radiation one needs to consider more particles in the simulation to see coherence effects. The results are compared with a python script, which loads the electron distribution from a hdf5 file generated by the PIC simulation [31]. The python algorithm works basically like the algorithm implemented in *PIConPGU*. It is known that this algorithm works, since it was verified with another python code which solves the integrals of the theoretical formula via Monte Carlo integration.

This simulation setup is based on the *Bunch* example setup of *PIConGPU*. In the bunch are 9977 particles. The bunch position distribution is generated as Gaussian normal distribution which is symmetric in the x- and z-axis with $\sigma = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$ and a bit thinner on the longitudinal axis with $\sigma_y = 3 \mu\text{m}$. Also the momentum is changed to move along the y-axis and the Lorentz factor is set to $\gamma_e = 100$ which is equal to the energy $E \approx 50 \text{ MeV}$. Since there is no need for the electric and magnetic field in the background, they are neglected again.

In fig. 4.3a the angular distribution of the intensity $dW/d\Omega$ is shown over the angle θ at frequency $\omega = 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\phi = 0$ rad for the PIC simulation and the python algorithm. The mean value of the absolute difference of both calculation methods is $\Delta_W = (5.2 \pm 24.4) \times 10^{-29}$ Js which is equal to $\Delta_{W,rel.} = (0.3 \pm 1.2)\%$ relative to the maximum intensity. The maximal absolute difference and the relative maximal difference are respectively is $\Delta_W^{max} = 1.8 \times 10^{-27}$ Js and $\Delta_{W,rel.}^{max} = 11.7\%$. Figure 4.3b shows, that the transition radiation calculated with the python code is slightly larger than the transition radiation calculated with the *CTR plugin*. This indicates that there is a systematic error.

4 Validating the PIC implementation

Figure 4.3: (a) shows the angular transition radiation distribution of a PIC simulation for an electron bunch and a python simulation for the same bunch. The polar angle is set to $\phi = 0$ rad and the detected radiation is $\omega = 10^{11}$ s $^{-1}$. (b) shows the difference between both methods.

This difference is currently suspected to origin from the python algorithm. The intensity in the longitudinal direction is zero due to the electron distribution not having a transversal spread.

Another interesting thing to look at is the radial symmetry of the bunch. In fig. 4.4a one can see the radiation intensity as a heatmap over the angles, which already looks symmetric. But to have a better understanding of the radial symmetry, the radiation values at the fixed azimuth angle $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$ were calculated to $W(\theta = 1/\gamma_e) = 1.9 \times 10^{-26}$ Js with the standard deviation of the values $\sigma_{W(\theta=1/\gamma_e)} = 4.8 \times 10^{-32}$ Js. This is 4 orders of magnitude smaller than the radiation intensity at this angle, so the radial symmetry is preserved by the plugin.

Since this simulation contains more than 1 particle, the coherence between these is an important factor. It leads to a cutoff at high frequencies $\omega = 2\pi c/\lambda$, as discussed in section 2.2. But first, something important to note is, that the distribution is heavily effected by the minimal weighting of the macro-particle in the PIC simulation. This leads to the sides of the distribution being cut off as shown in fig. 4.4b, since there would be less than one real particle in a macro-particle. Hence the truncated distribution has the size of $\Delta_z = 2 \mu\text{m}$. The longitudinal distribution of the electrons is shown in fig. 4.4b.

Figure 4.5 shows the high frequency cutoff from both the PIC simulation and the python calculation. There is a drop in intensity at $\omega \simeq 10^{15}$ s $^{-1}$, which is equal to $\lambda \simeq 2 \mu\text{m}$ and the characteristic length of the electron bunch. This means that at frequencies $\omega > 10^{15}$ s $^{-1}$, the phase difference between the electrons is getting larger than the wavelength of the radiation. Thus this radiation is just caused by the incoherent part of eq. (2.7). The intensity is now just scaling with $\propto N$ instead of $\propto N^2$. One can get the number of particles from the relative height difference between the coherent and the incoherent radiation in

Figure 4.4: (a) shows the radial symmetry of the PIC simulation for an electron bunch with $\gamma_e = 100$. (b) displays the longitudinal electron distribution of the bunch.

Figure 4.5: Incoherent and Coherent Parts of Transition Radiation and their effect to the total radiation with a changing frequency $\omega = 2\pi c/\lambda$ for an electron bunch with $N_e = 1000$ electrons with a velocity $\gamma_e = 100$ detected at $\theta = 1/\gamma_e$.

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Figure 4.6: Angular distribution of radiation with frequency $\omega = 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$ as a heatmap. Note that a detector angle $\theta > \pi/2$ rad means, that the detector is behind the foil.

the figure $10^{-26} \text{ Js}/10^{-29} \text{ Js} = 10^4$, which is equal to the amount of real particles in the PIC simulation.

Additionally there is a python simulation of the transition radiation created by this electron bunch put into this figure. The absolute difference of the python and the PIC results is $\Delta_W = (5.13 \pm 5.68) \times 10^{-28} \text{ Js}$, which is $\Delta_{W,rel.} = (2.6 \pm 2.9) \%$ to the maximum radiation intensity. The maximum absolute difference is $\Delta_W^{max} = 1.2 \times 10^{-28} \text{ Js}$, which is $\Delta_{W,rel.}^{max} = 6.2 \%$ relative to the local intensity. The error seems originate from the coherent part of the equation at $\omega < 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$. One also has to assume that the systematic error from fig. 4.3b is still present and the fact, that the error originates from the coherent part eq. (3.6), suggests that the error originates in the previously developed python code from loading the electron position from the hdf5 files.

In the region of $10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1} < \omega < 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the spectrum, a pseudoperiodic signature with decreasing intensity appears, which is caused by the coherent part of eq. (2.7). These signatures are similar to ringing artifacts can be explained by the similarity of the form factor to a Fourier transformation and the bunch shape. A Fourier transformation of a rectangle function looks like a $\text{sinc}(x) = \sin(x)/x$ function. Since the longitudinal bunch shape is a convolution of a normal distribution and a rectangle function, this ring effect appears and it is decreasing for higher $\omega > 5 \times 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ due to the angular resolution of the calculation.

In order to demonstrate the perpendicular amounts of transition radiation, the momentum vector of the electron bunch before was changed, since all previous simulations consider perfectly collimated, electron bunches moving perpendicular to the foil. The electron bunch now moves towards $\psi = \pi/4$ with the polar angle $\phi = \pi/2$. One now expects a radiation cone in moving direction of the electron bunch, but also a reflected cone at the same polar

Figure 4.7: Slices of fig. 4.6 at fixed azimuth angles θ for $\omega = 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$ compared with python results.

angle. Figure 4.6 shows the angular distribution of the electron bunch as a heatmap for the frequency $\omega = 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$. One can see the radiation peak in the moving direction at $\theta = \pi/4$ and $\phi = \pi/2$, but also the reflected radiation at $\theta = 3\pi/4$ and $\phi = \pi/2$.

To further compare this result with the previously used python algorithm, 3 slices with fixed azimuth angles θ of this heatmap were also calculated with python and compared in fig. 4.6. The slices were made at $\theta = \pi/8$, $\theta = \pi/2$ and $\theta = 3\pi/4$. In the latter slice one can see the local minimum of the radiation of the reflected cone at the exact polar angle $\phi/4$, which agrees with the previous results. The absolute differences between the PIC and the python algorithms are as shown in table 4.1. The maximal relative difference between PIC and the python code is $\Delta_{W,rel.}^{max} = 9.2\%$. Since this is still in the coherent regime of the transition radiation, the systematic error is being caused by the python code not respecting the position of the particles correctly.

The systematic difference for the many particles tests revealed a minor implementation error in the previously developed python code. Thus the differences in these tests between the *CTR plugin*, the python code and the analytic predictions are in the range of floating

Azimuth angle θ [rad]	$\pi/8$	$\pi/2$	$3\pi/4$
Δ_W	$(6.3 \pm 9.7) \times 10^{-34}$	$(1.4 \pm 2.4) \times 10^{-34}$	$(0.8 \pm 9.6) \times 10^{-29}$
$\Delta_{W,rel.} [\%]$	$(1.7 \pm 2.6) \times 10^{-3}$	$(3.1 \pm 5.3) \times 10^{-4}$	$(0.4 \pm 5.0) \times 10^{-1}$
Δ_W^{max}	3.4×10^{-33}	8.9×10^{-34}	1.5×10^{-27}
$\Delta_{W,rel.}^{max} [\%]$	9.4×10^{-3}	2×10^{-3}	9.2

Table 4.1: Absolute and relative absolute difference of PIC and python algorithm. The relative difference is relative to the maximum of radiation calculated by the PIC code for the corresponding angle ϕ .

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point precision and the plugin's transition radiation spectra are as expected. To further improve the numerical precision of the calculation, one could use 64 bit floating point precision variables in the plugin. From now on the plugin is used to calculate transition radiation in realistic physical setups.

5 Transition Radiation in LWFA PIC simulations

In this section laser wakefield accelerator simulations with two injection mechanisms were set up in *PIConGPU* to generate different electron bunches and subsequently calculate the transition radiation spectra with the *CTR plugin*. This is used to analyze the bunch structures. For consistency the coordinate system fig. 2.1a is used here and not the internal coordinate system of *PIConGPU*.

5.1 LWFA with bunch from self injection

In this section an electron bunch is generated from a laser wakefield accelerator based on self-injection. The simulation is based on the *LaserWakefield* example setup from *PIConGPU*. One can see the density profile of this PIC simulation in section 5.1. The plasma density profile is a 1120 μm long plateau with a 200 μm long linear slope leading up to the plateau and a 50 μm long downramp at the end into the vacuum. The electron density at the plateau is $5.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$. The laser propagates directly into the z direction, it has the wavelength $\lambda = 800 \text{ nm}$ and the normalized field strength $a_0 = 5.0$. Thus this simulation is accelerating an electron bunch in the nonlinear regime. The laser is linearly polarized on the on the y -axis and the focus is at 80 μm . The intensity profile of the laser has a Gaussian shape with the temporal standard deviation $\sigma = 4.25 \text{ fs}$.

Figure 5.1: Density profile of the plasma electrons in the PIC simulation for a self injected electron bunch.

Figure 5.2: Shows the electron density of the bunch created with self-injection with a greyscale. The darker an area is, the more electrons are in the area. The absolute electric field of the laser is shown with the red contour lines at an arbitrary level. Both the greyscale and as the contour line limits are constant over all times. The x-axis is the axis of the propagation direction, the y-axis is axis of the polarization direction of the laser. Both are in [μm]. Note that the frame is moving with the speed of light along the laser.

One can see the development of the electron bunch in section 5.1. When the laser enters the plasma at $t = 0.14$ ps, it pushes the electrons outward akin a snow plow and leaves an electron evacuated area behind. Due to the attractive Coulomb forces of this region, these electrons are pulled back again. The evacuated electrons come together at $t = 0.56$ ps creating the first bubble structures. The bubbles continue shrinking, since the density is continuing to increase, resulting in smaller bubbles at $t = 1.3$ ps. The plasma-wavelength for this density is $\lambda_p = 14.8 \mu\text{m}$, which is equal to the diameter of the bubbles. Note that the bubbles are electron-free, leaving a high electric field inside them. This, and the high electron density at the wake, lead to an injection of an electron bunch into the bubble, which is visible at $t = 3.8$ ps. The wake continuously injects electrons into the bunch and hence extends it longitudinally. There is also another injection in the second bubble with less electrons. Additionally the laser shape has changed, because of the optical focusing and defocusing effects of the laser interacting with the plasma. The electron bunch is accelerated until $t = 6.3$ ps and is ejected from the plasma. Its spatial dimensions are the longitudinal length $\Delta_l \simeq 15 \mu\text{m}$ and transverse width $\Delta_t \simeq 5 \mu\text{m}$. As the electron bunch propagates through the vacuum, the bunch diverges transversely, since it is not focused by the electric field inside the bubble anymore. At $t = 6.3$ ps the spatial spread of the main

i	0	1	2	3
t_i [ps]	1.4	3.5	4.9	6.9
z_i [mm]	0.4	1	1.5	2.1

Table 5.1: Timesteps for transition radiation calculation. Also the according propagation length $z = ct$ of the electron bunch relative to the ejection point of the plasma.

bunch is $\Delta'_l \simeq 10 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Delta'_t \simeq 15 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5.3a shows the energy distribution during the simulation as a histogram. One can see both injected electron bunches in this figure, as there are two distinct trajectories in the histogram. The first injection is injected at $t \simeq 1$ ps, the second one at $t \simeq 1.5$ ps. Since the injected electrons feel the same electric field in their bubbles, the bunches achieve a low energy-spread through the plasma acceleration. One can also see, that the acceleration of the electrons stops at $t \simeq 4.5$ ps when the bunch is leaving the plasma. The energy is also decreasing slightly after the electron bunch leaves the plasma. The first, main electron bunch is ejected with a smaller energy spread than the second electron bunch. This is probably caused by plasma-turbulence caused by the first ejection. The main electron bunch contains 5.7×10^8 particles in the range of 330 MeV to 360 MeV.

The transition radiation was calculated four times, once directly after electrons were injected into the bubble, once after 1.9 ps of acceleration in the plasma, once when the electron bunch is ejected from the plasma and finally when the bunch propagated for 2 ps through the vacuum. One can see the times of calculation and the according propagation lengths in table 5.1. The angular distribution of the radiation intensity over θ of these calculations is shown in fig. 5.3b. The intensity from the transition radiation is increasing as long as the bunch is accelerated and as soon as the bunch is ejected from the plasma,

Figure 5.3: (a) shows the energy distribution of the electrons over the time from the simulation. (b) shows the angular distribution of the transition radiation of the selfinjected electron bunch for the times from table 5.1. The angular distribution is emitted with the frequency $\omega = 1 \times 10^{12} \text{s}^{-1}$ at the angle $\phi = 0 \text{ mrad}$

t_i	t_0	t_1	t_2	t_3
θ'_{max} [mrad]	15.3 ± 0.8	16.9 ± 0.8	16.9 ± 0.8	18.4 ± 0.8
$\tilde{\gamma}_e$	65.1 ± 3.3	59.1 ± 2.7	59.1 ± 2.7	54.2 ± 2.3
\tilde{E} [MeV]	33.2 ± 1.7	30.2 ± 1.4	30.2 ± 1.4	27.7 ± 1.2

Table 5.2: Shows the difference $\theta'_{max} = \theta_{max} - \theta_{min}$ from fig. 5.3b, the approximation for the electron's Lorentz-factor $\tilde{\gamma}_e = 1/\theta'_{max}$ and the following approximation for the average electrons energy $\tilde{E} = \tilde{\gamma}_e m_e c^2$. The error from θ originates from the resolution of the simulation, the γ_e and E errors are calculated with $\Delta f(x) = (\partial f / \partial x) \Delta x$.

it loses kinetic energy and the radiation intensity decreases. The minimum is also not at $\theta_{min} = 0$ mrad, but at $\theta_{min} = 4.6$ mrad. This means, that the bunch doesn't hit the transition radiation foil perpendicularly, but under the angle ψ or it has a high divergence. The difference of θ_{max} and θ_{min} is shown in table 5.2 with the following approximations for the electron's Lorentz factor $\gamma_e = 1/\theta_{max}$ and energy $E = \gamma_e m_e c^2$. The stated error originates from the calculation resolution of the angular distribution θ . The energies calculated by this methods are not equal to the trajectories in fig. 5.3a. This is likely caused by the high energy spread of the bunch, leading to this redshift, since $\theta_{max} = 1/\gamma_e$ is only true for single particle transition radiation. Hence the energy determined with the angular distribution does not include the original energy within its error margins. This table also shows, that the energy decreases from t_2 to t_3 . Hence the electron bunch receives a decelerating force while ejecting from the plasma.

Figure 5.4 shows the transition radiation spectrum of this experiment for t_0 and t_2

Figure 5.4: Radiation spectrum of the self injected electron bunch calculated for the different timesteps listed in table 5.1. It is emitted at the observation angles θ_{max} and $\phi = 0$.

table 5.1. The radiation spectra change a lot from t_0 to t_2 . The main difference is the difference in intensity as already shown in fig. 5.3b. The intensity of the coherent radiation for t_0 drops off at $\propto 2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m} = 2 \mu\text{m}$. Due to the continuous self-injection into the bubble, the electron bunch grows longitudinally and the the intensity drop-off at t_2 is at $\propto 10^{-5} \text{ m} = 10 \mu\text{m}$. Thus the bunches longitudinal length is expected to be $\Delta_l \simeq 10 \mu\text{m}$, which agrees with the previously determined bunch length with section 5.1. At the drop-off different features develop at both time steps. For t_0 there are features in the spectrum at $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1} < \omega < 2 \times 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which lead to the assumption of longitudinal substructures $\propto 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. These features are not available in the spectrum from t_2 anymore. Hence these substructures likely disappear and we can assume a change of the particles spatial distribution for this propagation time.

If $\omega > 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$ the spectra become noisy, which is caused by the resolution of the transition radiation calculation. At $\omega \simeq 3 \times 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\omega \simeq 5 \times 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for t_0 and t_2 respectively the radiation spectral power stops decreasing and seems to transit to the incoherent regime. The amount of particle in the bunch can be approximated by dividing the intensity of radiation in the coherent regime by the intensity in the incoherent regime. This leads to $N_e \simeq 10^{-15} \text{ Js} / 10^{-21} \text{ Js} = 10^6$ particles for t_2 in the bunch, which does not agree to the previously determined amount of particles $N_e = 5.7 \times 10^8$ with the energy histogram fig. 5.3a. Since the according wavelengths at the lower plateaus are $\lesssim 6 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}$, they get into the order of magnitude of the grid-size of the simulation, which is $\Delta z = 4.4 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}$. The assumption, that the particles in a macro-particle in the simulation are at the same position is not correct anymore and one has to consider coherence effects within the macro-particle as shown in ref. [28]. One could also increase the length of this ramp in the spectrum by increasing the amount of macro-particles or decreasing the grid-size.

5.2 LWFA with bunch from downramp injection

This section analyzes an electron bunch accelerated in a plasma and injected with a downramp injection. The simulation is similar to the setup from section 5.1. Since it electrons are injected through a downramp, there is an additional plateau on top of the single-plateau density profile from the self-injection simulation. One can see the density profile of this PIC simulation in section 5.2. The first upramp is $200 \mu\text{m}$ long until the density 10^{25} m^{-3} is reached. This plateau is $80 \mu\text{m}$ long. Aferwards the first downramp is reached, setting the density over $17 \mu\text{m}$ to $5.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$. This plateau is $1100 \mu\text{m}$ long until it reaches another downramp into the vacuum, which is $50 \mu\text{m}$ long. The laser propagates directly into the z direction and it has the wavelength $\lambda = 800 \text{ nm}$, but it has a lower normalized field strength $a_0 = 2.5$ to prevent self-injection. It is also linearly polarized on the y -axis, its focus is at $60 \mu\text{m}$ and it has a Gaussian intensity profile with the temporal standard deviation $\sigma = 4.25 \text{ fs}$.

Section 5.2 shows the development of this this simulation. At $t = 0.56 \text{ ps}$ the laser beam has created partially electron-free bubbles in the upramp of the plasma. Due to the density increase the plasma wavelength λ_p decreases. Hence the wavelength of the generated plasma waves decreases as well. In the next figure at $t = 0.97 \text{ ps}$ the laser is close to reaching the downramp. The plasma waves have a smaller wavelength as in

Figure 5.5: Density profile of the plasma electrons in the PIC simulation for an electron bunch injected through a downramp.

Figure 5.6: Shows the electron density of the bunch created with a downramp injection with a greyscale. The darker an area is, the more electrons are in the area. The absolute electric field of the laser is shown with the red contour lines at an arbitrary level. Both the greyscale and the contour line limits are constant over all times. The x-axis is the axis of the propagation direction, the y-axis is axis of the polarization direction of the laser. Both are in $[\mu\text{m}]$. Note that the frame is moving with the speed of light along the laser.

i	0	1	2	3
t_i [ps]	2.1	3.5	4.9	6.9
z_i [mm]	0.6	1	1.5	2.1

Table 5.3: Timesteps for transition radiation calculation. Also the according propagation length of the electron bunch relative to the ejection point of the plasma.

the figure before due to higher density. The plasma wavelength is $\lambda_p = 10.6 \mu\text{m}$, which is also the diameter of the bubbles at $t = 0.97 \text{ ps}$. At $t = 1.1 \text{ ps}$ the electrons at the wake potential got injected into the first bubble, which is now larger $\lambda_p = 14.8 \mu\text{m}$ due to the density decrease. At $t = 2.1 \text{ ps}$ one can see, that the laser is not able to evacuate the first bubble anymore. This means that the laser's intensity is not high enough or the laser pulse is not long enough. Due to the relatively low intensity of the laser, its electromagnetic field is not strong enough to evacuate the bubble. The electron bunch is now a driver for plasma-waves and creates a bubble behind it. At $t = 4.9 \text{ ps}$ the laser intensity is decreased a lot, since its energy decreases. The electron bunch is still ejected and its transverse size increases while propagating in the vacuum as seen in $t = 6.3 \text{ ps}$. This increase in transverse size shows that the electric fields in the plasma were still focussing the electron bunch. The longitudinal and transverse bunch size increases from $\Delta_l \simeq 3 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Delta_t \simeq 10 \mu\text{m}$ at $t = 4.9 \text{ ps}$ to $\Delta'_l \simeq 3 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Delta'_t \simeq 15 \mu\text{m}$ at $t = 6.3 \text{ ps}$ as read off the figure.

Another feature in this simulation is the second, not transversely centered wave, which is visible at $t = 4.9 \text{ ps}$, which is also ejected from the plasma later. After propagating through the vacuum, these ejected electrons are centering on the z-axis again.

Figure 5.7a shows the distribution of the energies during the simulation as a histogram. At $t \simeq 4.5 \text{ ps}$ the acceleration of the electrons stops and the electrons lose energy slowly. Thus the electrons do not gain energy anymore and drift with a slowly decreasing velocity for the rest of the simulation. There are 2 main injections, one at $t = 2 \text{ ps}$ and the other one at $t = 3 \text{ ps}$. The latter contains less particles than the first injection. The first, higher energy bunch will be assumed to be the main downramp injection from section 5.2, the second trajectory will be associated with the electrons which were accelerated by the wake driven from the first bunch and then got separated transversely. There are also electrons injected at $t = 1.5 \text{ ps}$, but the energy spreads a lot, which means that no high quality bunch is ejected. Contrary to fig. 5.3a, not only the energy from the main particle bunch keeps its small spread after the ejection $t \simeq 4.5 \text{ ps}$, but also the spread of the second injection stays relatively small. In the bunch are $N_e \gtrsim 10^8$ electrons, calculated by a sum over all bins with $60 \text{ MeV} < E < 80 \text{ MeV}$. Electrons with an energy lower than $E \lesssim 50 \text{ MeV}$ are neglected in the transition radiation calculation due to a γ_e filter at $\gamma_e = 100$.

Figure 5.7b shows the angular distribution of the transition radiation for this simulation for 4 different propagation times, directly after the injection, after some acceleration time, after the ejection from the plasma and after propagation through the vacuum as shown in table 5.3. As in section 5.1, the intensity of the transition radiation increases until it reaches the vacuum. This bunch is centered on the z-axis due to the minimum at $\theta = 0$. Table 5.4 shows θ_{max} according to the maximum of the transition radiation intensity from fig. 5.7b and the respective Lorentz factor $\gamma_e = 1/\theta_{max}$ and the energy $E = \gamma_e mc^2$. The stated error is determined by the resolution of the angular distribution. As in section 5.1 the difference between the actual electron energy and the energy calculated with the angular distribution

Figure 5.7: (a) shows the energy histogram as an energy over time diagram, with the amount of particles per MeV shown in the bin. (b) shows the angular distribution of the transition radiation of the selfinjected electron bunch for the times from table 5.3. The observed frequency is $\omega = 1 \times 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at the polar angle $\phi = 0 \text{ mrad}$

is caused by $\gamma_e = 1/\theta_{max}$ being only true for single particle transition radiation.

Figure 5.8 shows the transition radiation spectrum of these bunches calculated at t_0 and t_2 from table 5.1. The main difference is the total intensity, which was already noticed in fig. 5.7b. There is a ring substructure for $2 \times 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1} < \omega < 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at t_2 . Thus the bunch has developed a large spatial substructure, which could be equal to the two smaller bunches noticed in section 5.2. These two bunches are $\propto 20 \mu\text{m}$ apart from each other. At $\propto 6 \times 10^{14} \text{ s}^{-1}$ the coherent part of the transition radiation drops for the accelerated bunch t_2 . Hence one can assume a bunch length of $\Delta_l \simeq 2 \mu\text{m}$, which agrees with the previously determined bunch length from section 5.2. It drops at $\propto 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is similar to section 5.1, where the bunch gets focused during the propagation in the plasma. At $10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1} < \omega < 7 \times 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$ different spectrum features develop with the electron propagation, meaning that the sub bunch structures change with the propagation. In this regime one can see that the coherent radiation becomes more dominant again. Hence there

t_i [ps]	t_0	t_1	t_2	t_3
θ_{max} [mrad]	17.7 ± 0.8	12.3 ± 0.8	10.8 ± 0.8	11.5 ± 0.8
$\tilde{\gamma}_e$	56.6 ± 2.5	81.3 ± 5.1	92.9 ± 6.6	86.8 ± 5.8
\tilde{E} [MeV]	28.9 ± 1.3	41.6 ± 2.6	47.5 ± 3.4	44.3 ± 3.0

Table 5.4: Shows θ_{max} for the maximum of fig. 5.3b, the approximation for the electrons Lorentz-factor $\tilde{\gamma}_e = 1/\theta_{max}$ and the following approximation for the average electrons energy $\tilde{E} = \tilde{\gamma}_e m_e c^2$. The error from θ originates from the resolution of the simulation, the γ_e and E errors are calculated with $\Delta f(x) = (\partial f/\partial x) \Delta x$.

Figure 5.8: Radiation spectrum of the self injected electron bunch calculated for the different timesteps listed in table 5.1. The observation angles are θ_{max} and $\phi = 0$.

is a probably another spatial feature in the electron bunch $\propto 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ like microbunching, which would require further examination. Since these features already appear at t_0 , these sub structures are already generated with the electron injection. If $\omega > 7 \times 10^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$ the coherent part of the transition radiation decreases again, leading to a second dropoff until $\omega \simeq 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$. At higher radiations the frequency resolution is not large enough anymore to show features and the emitted radiation equals noise. In this frequency region $\omega > 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ the transition radiation creates the lower plateau. One can divide the height of the coherent radiation plateau with of the lower, incoherent transition radiation plateau to get the number of electrons $N_e = 10^{-17} \text{ Js} / 10^{-23} \text{ Js} = 10^6$. This number is smaller than the previously determined number of electrons again, due to the previously discussed form factor issue. But the radiation minimum at $\omega = 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for t_2 shows that the incoherent radiation, which is a frequency independent constant, is lower than the roughly estimated position of the plateau at 10^{-23} Js . Since $\omega = 10^{16} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is in the regime of the simulations grid size $\Delta z = 4.4 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}$, the particles within a macro-particle ensemble are assumed to be fully coherent again, which leads to more coherent transition radiation as expected.

6 Outlook and conclusion

Further development

The *CTR Plugin* computes coherent and incoherent transition radiation according to theory, as long as the observed frequency is small compared to the cell size. The plugin already can be used for production runs and is fully accessible by *PICongPU*-input files, so that everyone should be able to use it. For this, the code is going to be audited and merged to the mainline of *PICongPU*. One minor limitation of the current implementation, as noted in section 5.1 and section 5.2, is that the coherent part of the transition radiation assumes that all particles within a macro-particle are at the same position. Thus the phase difference of the coherent transition radiation originating from these electrons is zero for all frequencies. Therefore the transition radiation from all physical electrons represented by each macroparticle are fully coherent to each other, respectively. However, this is not physical, since multiple electrons can not have the exact same position, and it leads to a slightly higher intensity in the incoherent regime of the radiation spectrum. Hence the macro-particle form factor has to be included in the transition radiation kernel respecting the spatial distribution of the particles in the ensemble.

One useful feature for comparisons with experiments would be to define a virtual transition radiation foil surface, not at the current position, but further downstream at a later point in time. For this one would add some simple particle tracking, assuming vacuum and no fields, in order to let electrons “virtually” propagate to the foil and calculate the transition radiation at this point. Such a feature would allow to model electrons after some vacuum propagation, approximating how the divergence modifies the form factor, as discussed in section 5.1 or section 5.2. But instead of continuing to run the simulation over mm to 10s of mm longer, until the bunch reaches the foil, one can run the simulation just until the electrons are ejected from the plasma and hence save simulation time. Another useful extension would be to explicitly include inclinations of the metal foils surface, since many experiments use tilted metal foils (e.g. at 45 degrees). Although the implemented *CTR plugin* implicitly already includes this possibility, it is helpful to also include an abstraction layer that parameterizes the foil geometry and the observation directions using rotation matrices.

Since the plugin can be used not only for spectra, but for images instead of spectra (i.e. a grid of observation directions at one frequency), it will be advantageous to add png and hdf5 to the suite of output formats. Especially for hdf5, it will be easy to also save the complex-valued value of the transition radiation amplitudes before taking the modulus square together with the meta data from foil geometry and angular resolution information. This complex-valued data with meta data will enable to calculate in post-processing the transition radiation near-field, as observed by experiments which directly image a transition

radiation foil to a CCD camera. Finally, for further optimizing kernel performance, it would be beneficial to also parallelize over the observed transition radiation frequencies, in addition to the observation directions.

Conclusion

The aim of this thesis, was to create an in-situ plugin for *PICongPU*, which calculates transition radiation fast. The *CTR plugin* can compute a high resolution transition radiation spectrum of an electron bunch containing a million macro-particles on one GPU per observation direction within a second due to the high parallelization of the calculation. The plugin was compared with the transition radiation theory, resulting in an average error $< 1\%$ caused by the numerical precision of floating point numbers.

Furthermore two LWFA simulations, one with a self-injected and one with a downramp injected electron bunch, were analyzed with the help of transition radiation spectra created at various timesteps of the simulations. Here it was possible to observe the longitudinal bunch growth due to the continuing injection of the self-injected bunch and it was also possible to observe the development of spectrum features caused by substructures in the bunch's longitudinal structure from the downramp-injection. A typical physical experiment usually measures the transition radiation of an electron bunch behind a laser-plasma accelerator, when the bunch has already entered the vacuum. However, the *CTR plugin* allows to measure the transition radiation at multiple different timesteps of the simulation, such as directly after the electron-injection from an LWFA. This is especially useful, when one needs to identify the initial physics cause of some specific spectral feature of a transition radiation spectrum and to observe its subsequent laser-plasma-bunch evolution and propagation.

Beyond direct comparisons to experimental data, the *CTR plugin* can also be used to quickly generate large quantities of artificial datasets of particle distributions on the one hand with CTR spectra on the other hand. These datasets enable benchmarking and training phase retrieval algorithms, e.g. machine-learning based algorithms, for reconstructing the 3D spatial electron distribution from the spectral transition radiation intensity (without spectral phase). Such algorithms again improve both quality and speed in experimental data analysis for longitudinal and transverse electron bunch shape [32–34].

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Erklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit im Rahmen der Betreuung am Institut für Kern- und Teilchenphysik ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter verfasst habe und alle verwendeten Quellen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Ort, Datum

Unterschrift